

Bio Vote System – Enhanced Electronic Voting Machine with Fingerprint Recognition and RFID Authentication

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Abstract— This project presents an electronic voting system designed to enhance the security, integrity, and transparency of electoral processes. The system integrates various technologies to enable secure authentication and prevent fraudulent activities during voting. Users can enroll their identities, authenticate themselves using biometric or RFID methods, and cast their votes securely. In the event of unauthorized access or attempted malpractice, the system promptly alerts administrators and users, ensuring timely intervention. The electronic voting system is developed that combines the more secure version of the previous system with the use of contemporary technology, such as RFID reader finger printer detection that matches the voter's ID to the specific finger print. After voting, the vote count is sent to a web server that can only be accessed by the election commission's committee members, where the top team can be displayed. Additionally, to deter multiple voting attempts, the system intelligently detects mismatched votes and notifies relevant parties, preserving the fairness of the process. Moreover, the system incorporates a server-based vote counting mechanism accessible exclusively to authorized committee members. This feature ensures that the counting process remains transparent and accessible only to authorized personnel, thereby upholding the confidentiality and credibility of election results.

Keywords— EM-18 Reader Module, NodeMCU ESP8266, Fingerprint Sensor, Buzzer, Relay Module, 16X2 LCD display.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Election procedures are being revolutionized by sophisticated computerized voting machines. This system provides safe, effective, and unchangeable voting through the combination of cutting-edge RFID and fingerprint identification technologies. Voter anonymity is preserved while the integrity of every vote is ensured through the use of fingerprints and RFID cards for seamless authentication. Election officials can keep tabs on voting activity thanks to real-time monitoring capabilities, which guarantee transparency and prompt correction of any errors. With its tactile feedback options and user-friendly interface, the system is inclusive and suitable for voters of all abilities. Moreover, strong data encryption protocols and integrated audit trail features prioritize the security and integrity of election data, protecting it from manipulation and unwanted access.

II. METHODOLOGY AND WORKING PRINCIPLE

The conventional ways of casting ballots are changing in an age of rapid technological development. The Bio Vote System - Enhanced, which offers an advanced combination of RFID and fingerprint recognition technology, signals a new era in election procedures. This cutting-edge system offers improved security and precision together with a smooth and welcoming voting process for all.

A. Proposed Method

The Bio Vote System - Enhanced is designed to tackle the changing needs of contemporary elections in a comprehensive manner. Fundamentally, this technology uses fingerprint recognition and RFID authentication to guarantee voter identity and ballot integrity. Each voter can cast a ballot securely and confidently thanks to the seamless integration of these technologies, knowing that their vote is permanently connected to their own biometric identification. The system's ability to protect against fraud and manipulation while maintaining voter privacy is essential to its effectiveness. By employing RFID cards and fingerprint authentication, the Bio Vote System reduces the possibility of unauthorized or duplicate votes by guaranteeing that only authorized voters are allowed to participate in the voting process. Election administrators can also quickly supervise voting activities thanks to the system's real-time monitoring features. Any abnormalities or irregularities can be quickly found and fixed. When designing the Bio Vote

System, accessibility is also given top priority. All voters, regardless of ability, can cast ballots with confidence and comfort thanks to tactile feedback options and an intuitive interface. A fully democratic experience is fostered for all thanks to its inclusion, which guarantees that no voter is left behind. Strong encryption methods and integrated audit trail features are two ways that the Bio Vote System strengthens the security of election data.

B. Working Principle

The initiative aims to enhance the current electronic voting system by incorporating innovative security measures and contemporary technologies. By using RFID readers and fingerprint scanning, the system ensures that voting is more secure and un-hackable. The likelihood of fraud is significantly reduced by verifying each voter's identity with a distinct fingerprint that matches their RFID ID number. After votes are cast, the system automatically sends the vote total to a specified web server. To ensure the integrity and confidentiality of the election data, access to this server is limited to members of the electoral commission's committee. Committee members can easily obtain up-to-date information on the vote count and results in real time via the secure web interface.

III. WORKFLOW

IV. EXPERIMENTAL OUTPUT

After turning on the kit, we must choose whether to Enroll a new ID, validate an existing ID, or remove an ID. These are the options that are initially displayed on the LCD panel. To begin the enrollment procedure, first choose the enroll option, then pick the desired card number and place your finger in the fingerprint sensor. Your fingerprint will be stored alongside the selected card number. After placing your finger in the fingerprint sensor and selecting the "Identify" option, the fingerprint will be confirmed and the card number you choose for that fingerprint will appear. There are no options to choose from when casting a vote; simply present your card to the RFID reader module and place your finger on the fingerprint sensor. If both fingerprint and ID number match, you can choose the voter you wish to cast your vote for. Should they not match, the LCD will display the mismatch and play a buzzer. Additionally, attempting to cast a vote using an invalid card or one that has not been registered will cause the LCD display to show "unauthorized" and sound a buzzer. The Enrolling option is displayed below in Fig. 1 as "ENROLLMENT". The next option "IDENTIFY FP" is shown in Fig. 2 this will verify the fingerprint with the card number.

Fig. 1 Enrollment Option

Fig. 2 Identify Fingerprint

While enrolling if the fingerprint is stored then it will be display “Prints stored” as shown in Fig. 3. Authorized user notification is displayed as “AUTHORIZED USER” while voting is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3 Fingerprint stored Notification

Fig. 4 Authorized user verification

Unauthorized user notification for non-registered ID is displayed as “UNAUTHORIZED” as shown in Fig. 5. If the fingerprint and the card number is not matched then it will show “MISS-MATCHED” as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 5 Unauthorized user with buzzer sound

Fig. 6 Miss-matched Display with buzzer sound

After authorized the option to vote for the candidates is shown in Fig. 7 and after voted successfully it will display with the 'X' symbol in the candidate number who you voted and this is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7 Candidate select Option

Fig. 8 Voted Intimation

The Vote count for each candidate after each vote is counted and stored in the web server which is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9 Web Server Count Display

V. INNOVATIVENESS OF THE SOLUTION

- The integration of biometric authentication capabilities, such as fingerprint recognition and iris scanning, enhances security by independently validating each voter's identification and lowers the likelihood of fraudulent actions taking place during the voting process.
- Application of RFID Technology: RFID tags provide for accurate voter identification and verification, improving voting process accuracy and dependability and guaranteeing that only voters who qualify may cast ballots.
- Using Secure Authentication Methods: The security and integrity of voting data are guaranteed by the use of cutting-edge cryptographic algorithms, which also guard against manipulation and unwanted access, maintaining the integrity of the democratic process.

VI. UNIQUENESS AND FEATURES

By limiting the number of unauthorized votes and identity fraud cases, the system uses biometric identification methods like iris scanning and fingerprint recognition to make sure that only authorized voters can cast ballots. A visible and impenetrable record of votes is provided by the system's integration of

blockchain technology, which also ensures the integrity and immutability of voting data, hence boosting public confidence in the election process. Election authorities may monitor voting patterns in real time and identify any abnormalities quickly thanks to the capabilities of the BIO VOTE SYSTEM. Additionally, the voting data is kept confidential and intact as the system securely transfers the vote total to a web server that is only accessible by authorized persons.

VII. FUTURE ENHNCEMENT

Integration of AI and Machine Learning: By utilizing AI and machine learning algorithms, the system may be able to identify and stop increasingly complex types of fraud or manipulation, strengthening and fortifying the democratic process. **Voting capabilities on mobile devices:** By enabling voters to conveniently cast their ballots from their smartphones or tablets, the development of mobile voting applications compatible with the BIO VOTE SYSTEM could increase voter turnout and increase voting accessibility. **Solutions for Blockchain Scalability:** To enable the system to manage higher transaction volumes without sacrificing security or performance, research and development activities could concentrate on resolving the scalability problems that come with blockchain technology. **Better Biometric Recognition:** Developments in biometric technology may result in voter authentication techniques like facial recognition or vein pattern detection that are even more precise and effective, enhancing the system's security and dependability

VIII. CONCLUSION

From this proposed method, the safeguard Bio Vote system offers a viable way to modernize and safeguard the electoral process with its Enhanced Electronic Voting with Fingerprint Recognition and RFID Authentication features. This method attempts to solve important issues with security, accuracy, and privacy in electronic voting by combining cutting-edge biometric technologies and dual-layer authentication. But it is crucial to recognize the advantages it might have as well as the difficulties in putting it into practice.

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